

obvious that we have to find D discrete subset of B which its closure containing this limit point, but no discrete subset from B whose elements converges to (∞_e, ∞_0) .

(∞_e, ∞_0) is a limit point of B. Let $S \in \mathfrak{S}_0$, $S = \{x_1, x_2, \dots\}$. Then $x_n \rightarrow S$ in X_0^* , but x_n is eventually outside each basic compact set in X_e^* . Thus $x_n \rightarrow \infty_e$ in X_e^* . Thus $(\infty_e, S) \in \overline{B}$ for each $S \in \mathfrak{S}_0$. Let S_n be a sequence of distinct elements in $\mathfrak{S}_0$. Then for each n, $(\infty_e, S_n) \in \overline{B}$ and $(\infty_e, S_n) \rightarrow (\infty_e, \infty_0)$ in $X_e^* \times X_0^*$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

No sequence in B covers to (∞_e, ∞_0) . Let (x_n, x_n) be a sequence of distinct points in B. Since $\mathfrak{S}_e \cup \mathfrak{S}_0$ is a maximal almost disjoint collection of infinite sets in X the sequence $(x_n : n = 1, 2, \dots)$ is either frequently in some $S \in \mathfrak{S}_e$ (and thus has a subsequence

convergent to $S \in X_e^*$) or it is frequently in some $S \in \mathfrak{S}_0$ (and has a subsequence convergent to $S \in X_0^*$). Thus $(x_n : n = 1, 2, \dots)$ cannot tend both to ∞_e in X_e^* and ∞_0 in X_0^* .

Theorem is proved.

References

1. Angelo Bella, Petr Simon "Spaces which are generated by discrete sets". Topology and its Applications, 135, 2004, pp.87-99.
2. Boehme T. K., Rosenfeld M. "An example of two compact Frechet Hausdorff spaces, whose product is not Frechet" London Math. Soc., 8, 1974, pp.339-344.
3. Dow A., Tkachenko M. G., Tkachuk V. V., Wilson R. G. "Topologies generated by discrete subspaces". Glasnik Matematicki, 37(57), 2002, pp.189-212.
4. Engelking R. "General Topology", PWN, Warszawa, 1977.

UDC 539.3

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE CURVILINEAR MOTION OF THE CAR, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE ELASTICITY AND DEFORMABILITY OF TIRES

Dusmatov O.M.,

Samarkand State University, 15 University blv., 140104, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Mamatkabilov A.Kh.

Termiz State University, 43 Faizulla Khodjaev str., 190111, Termiz, Uzbekistan.

Abstract

The paper proposes a mathematical model of a curvilinear motion of the car, taking into account an elastic characteristic of tires and the characteristics of their interaction with the road, as well as the design features of the front suspension and steering system based on the dynamics of rolling systems. The obtained mathematical model makes it possible to fully study the dynamics and stability of systems, taking into account design parameters.

Keywords: mathematical model, motion, rolling, deformation, elasticity, tire, potential forces, kinetic energy.

Introduction

An increase in the number of vehicles and an increase in traffic intensity lead to the need to improve their reliability and safety.

The modernization of vehicles, the active introduction of automatic control elements in various components of vehicles requires an assessment of the impact of all introduced improvements on the behavior of the car.

On the one hand, the development of computer technologies associated with analytical transformations makes it possible to consider vehicle models with a large number of degrees of freedom.

One of the most important of these problems is to determine the dependence of certain dynamic properties of systems, for example, stability or the nature of the loss of stability, on certain parameters of the problem.

Recent study [1] has shown that a reasonable reduction in the number of degrees of freedom and parameters taken into account does not significantly affect a number of practically important motion parameters. This indicates the need for the most complete study of the properties of simple car models and an increase in the number of degrees of freedom and the number of parameters taken into account only if necessary.

Of particular importance among the elements of the car, which largely determine its dynamics, is the pneumatic tire due to its role as a link between the crew and the road. All relevant forces for acceleration, braking, curvilinear motion are realized through the force interaction between the tire and the road. Despite the boundless number of works, the subject of which was the pneumatic tire, due to the complexity of its properties, the study of the influence of tire properties on the dynamics of the car continues to be one of the most urgent problems of mechanics.

On the one hand, research is underway to take into account all tire parameters more and more, on the other hand, the phenomenological theory of rolling has been built [2], which allows, with a decrease in at least an order of the number of parameters taken into account, to build the tire model that takes into account the general case of deformation and which makes it possible to obtain, as special cases, all previously known models of the rolling theory of N.Rocard, M.V.Keldysh, etc.

The current level of development of the rolling theory and computer software makes it possible to consider the car model of almost any complexity, at the same time, it cannot provide an analysis of the influence of numerous constant and physical parameters of the problem on the stability of the motion with their formally qualified application, which is due to the extreme complexity of the problem under consideration.

Therefore, there is a need to develop the computer system to automate the output of the mathematical model and study the stability of the car motion. Such a system for studying the stability of the car motion can be used for any model of the car and any motion, if the corresponding characteristic equations are explicitly written for it, for which it is necessary to obtain an explicit form of the equations of perturbed motion with first approximation.

Nowadays, there are certain results on automating the stage of compiling the equations of perturbed motion of complex nonlinear mechanical systems, both using standard systems for processing symbolic information, like Maple, and original procedures. The need to automate this stage of the study is largely due to the fact that for curvilinear motion, in contrast to the case of rectilinear motion, the parameters of unperturbed motion at the same linear speed of the car and the applied traction will change depending on the chosen model of interaction between the tire and the road. With the automatic compilation of equations of perturbed motion, it is possible to proceed to the next stage - automation of determining the level of modeling - the number and choosing the degrees of freedom and parameters that are not only sufficient, but also necessary for an adequate description of the vehicle dynamics. Automation of determining the level of modeling should provide the possibility of analyzing the influence of certain parameters of the car, on its dynamics, in particular, the stability of the motion. The ranges of changes in the design parameters of the car are divided into small intervals, for which a computational experiment is carried out with a successive simplification of the model.

Then, for each interval, the most significant parameters are distinguished by recognition methods, on the basis of which a simplified model of the car is automatically built for the corresponding set of parameter values and a complex model is based.

To solve this problem, this paper solves the problem of developing a mathematical model of the curvilinear motion of wheeled transport vehicles (using the example of a car), taking into account the elasticity and deformability of tires.

Materials and methods

Consider the motion of the car under the following assumptions:

the car body - a solid body mounted on four linear springs with linear dampers;

the center of gravity of the front dependent suspension with steered wheels is at the same distance from the wheels;

the wheels are dynamically balanced, their median planes are always parallel;

the axes of pivots, swivel pins are set at angles to the vertical, both in the longitudinal and transverse planes;

the axis of the front suspension of the car, elastically connected with the body, can rotate around the longitudinal axis of the car;

the front wheels are rigidly connected to each other and rotate around the pivots simultaneously through angles $\mathcal{G}_1$ and $\mathcal{G}_2$;

the rear wheels are also rigidly connected to each other, transversely inclined, and their camber angles can be the same.

Let us introduce the following notation:

x, y, z are coordinates of the center of mass of the car; θ is the angle of rotation of the car around the vertical axis; $\mathcal{G}_1$ and $\mathcal{G}_2$ are angles of the rotation of the front wheels around the pivots, counted from the direction of the longitudinal axis of the vehicle. The positive direction of the angles $\theta, \mathcal{G}_1$ and $\mathcal{G}_2$ corresponds to turning the wheels to the left; ψ is the angle of the rotation of the front suspension axle together with the wheels around the longitudinal axis of the vehicle. The positive value of the angle corresponds to the lift of the left wheel; γ_0 is angle of longitudinal inclination of the pin. It is positive when the upper end of the pin is moved back; β_0 is the angle of the transverse inclination of the pin. It is considered positive if the upper end of the pin is displaced inside the track; β is the angle of the transverse inclination of the rear wheels. It is considered positive if the top of the wheel is shifted inward; ν is angle of longitudinal inclination of the body; τ is the angle of the transverse inclination of the body; m is the mass of the car; m_1 is the mass of the rear of the car without wheels and front suspension; m_{2i} is mass of the i -th wheel; m_3 is the mass of the front suspension of the car; l is distance from the center of mass of the front suspension to the center of the pivot; l_1 is distance from the center of mass of the car to its front axle; l_2 is distance from the center of mass of the car to its rear axle; l_3 is distance from the center of the pin to the center of the wheel; $L=l_1+l_2$ is car base; $L_1=l+l_3$ is distance from the center of mass of the front suspension to the center of the vehicle wheel (half-track); A_i is the moment of inertia of the i -th wheel with the hub and a brake drum relative to its diameter; B is the moment of inertia of the front suspension about an axis perpendicular to it and passing through the center of mass (central moment of inertia of the front suspension); C_i is axial moment of inertia of the i -th wheel; D is the moment of inertia of the rear of the car without front suspension and wheels relative to the axis passing through its center of mass; J_1 is the moment of inertia of the car without front wheels relative to the vertical axis passing through the center of mass of the car; J_2 is the moment of inertia of the front wheels relative to the pin axis; J_3 is the moment of

inertia of the front suspension with steerable wheels relative to the longitudinal axis of the vehicle; K_1 is angular stiffness of the steering system; K_2 is angular rigidity along the coordinate ψ ; h_{1i} is coefficient of viscous friction in steering; h_{2i} is coefficient of viscous friction along the coordinate ψ ; K_2^l is angular rigidity of the rod device; C_{pc} is coefficient of elasticity of the spring; C_{sh} is radial stiffness of the tire; L_{rs} is distance from the center of mass of the suspension to the spring; h_{sh} is internal resistance of the tire; h_a is internal resistance of the vibration absorber; h_{rs} is internal resistance of the springs; h_c is the coefficient of viscous friction of the rod device; α_i is kinematic parameter of the i -th tire associated with the lateral deformation of the tire; β_i is kinematic parameter of the i -th tire associated with the angular deformation of the tire; γ_i is kinematic parameter of the i -th tire associated with the angle of the wheel; a_i is coefficient of lateral stiffness of the i -th tire; b_i is coefficient of angular stiffness of the i -th tire; σ_i is coefficient of elasticity of the tire associated with the lateral deformation of the i -th tire; ρ_i is coefficient of elasticity of the i -th tire associated with the angle of inclination of the wheel; r_i is rolling radius of the i -th tire; ξ_i is lateral deformation of the i -th tire; φ_i is angular deformation of the i -th tire; χ_i is angle of inclination of the i -th wheel; η_i is longitudinal deformation of the i -th

tire; Δ_i is angle of rotation around its axis of the i -th wheel ($i=1,4$); $r_{0i}=const$.

Result and discussion

Let us assume that for small deviations of the car from the motion with speed V along the Oy axis, there is no tire slip on the road. In this case $\dot{\Delta}_i = \frac{V}{r_i}$. The

dynamic system under consideration consists of six interconnected bodies: four wheels, the front dependent suspension and the rear of the car without front suspension and wheels (Fig. 1).

The tire deformation parameters $\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3, \xi_4, \varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3, \varphi_4, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4$, where index 1 and 2 refer to the left and right front wheels, index 3 and 4 refer to the left and right rear wheels (Fig. 2). Coordinates of the center of masses of the left $C_1(x_{03}, y_{03}, z_{03})$ and right $C(x_{04}, y_{04}, z_{04})$ front wheels, the center of mass of the front suspension $O(x_{01}, y_{01}, z_{01})$, the center of mass of the rear axle $B(x_{02}, y_{02}, z_{02})$, center of gravity of the left $D_1(x_{05}, y_{05}, z_{05})$ and right $D(x_{06}, y_{06}, z_{06})$ rear wheels are expressed in terms of the generalized coordinates $\theta, \vartheta_1, \vartheta_2, \psi, x, y, z$ of the vehicle.

Fig.1. Frame view of the vehicle.

To do this, we introduce the following coordinate systems:

1) $OXYZ$ with the beginning in the middle of the front axle, the OY axis is directed along the velocity vector V , OZ is directed upwards;

2) $O_1X_1Y_1Z_1$ with the origin in the center of the left wheel pin, axis O_1X_1 , which coincides with the front axle, and axis O_1Y_1 is parallel to the speed V ;

3) $O_2X_2Y_2Z_2$ with the beginning in the center of the pin of the right wheel, the axis O_2Z_2 coincides with the pin;

4) $O_1X_3Y_3Z_3$ the axes of this coordinate system are rotated by an angle ϑ_1 around the axis $O_1Z_2=O_1Z_3$ relative to the coordinate system $O_2X_2Y_2Z_2$;

5) $O_1X_4Y_4Z_4$ the axes of this coordinate system are rotated by an angle β_0 around the $O_1Y_3=O_1Y_4$ axis, so that the O_1X_4 axis coincides with the axis of the left wheel hub.

Fig.2. Tire deformation.

Let the coordinates of the vector $\vec{r}(x_4, y_4, z_4)$ be given in the coordinate system $O_1X_4Y_4Z_4$. Then, in the coordinate system $O_1X_3Y_3Z_3$, the coordinates of the same vector can be defined in matrix form as follows:

$$[x_3] = A_4[x_4], \quad (1)$$

where $[x_3] = [x_3, y_3, z_3]^T$ is a column matrix of coordinates of vector $\vec{r}$ in the coordinate system $O_1X_3Y_3Z_3$; $[x_4]$ is column matrix of coordinates of the vector $\vec{r}$ in the coordinate system $O_1X_4Y_4Z_4$, the index "T" means the operation of matrix transposition.

Expanding the cosine and sine functions into a series and leaving only linear terms, we get:

$$A_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & -\beta_0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \beta_0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ is transition matrix from coordinate system } O_1X_4Y_4Z_4 \text{ to coordinate system The}$$

elements a_{ij} ($i, j=1,2,3$) of matrix A_4 are the direction cosines of the axes of the coordinate system $O_1X_4Y_4Z_4$ with respect to the coordinate system $O_1X_3Y_3Z_3$.

Similarly, to transform coordinates from system $O_1X_3Y_3Z_3$ to system $O_1X_2Y_2Z_2$, we have

$$[x_2] = A_3[x_3], \quad (2)$$

where $[x_2] = [x_2, y_2, z_2]^T$ is the column matrix of vector coordinates $\vec{r}$ in the coordinate system

$$O_1X_2Y_2Z_2; A_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\vartheta_1(t) & 0 \\ \vartheta_1(t) & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \text{ is transition matrix from coordinate system } O_1X_3Y_3Z_3 \text{ to coordi-}$$

nate system $O_1X_2Y_2Z_2$.

The elements a_{ij} ($i, j=1,2,3$) of matrix A_3 are the direction cosines of the axes of the coordinate system $O_1X_3Y_3Z_3$ with respect to the coordinate system $O_1X_2Y_2Z_2$.

Substituting (1) in expression (2), we obtain

$$[x_2] = A_3A_4[x_4].$$

In a similar way, for 5 coordinate systems, we can write

$$[x] = A_1A_2A_3A_4[x_4],$$

where $A_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \beta_0 \\ 0 & 1 & -\gamma_0 \\ -\beta_0 & \gamma_0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ is transition matrix from coordinate system $O_1X_2Y_2Z_2$ to coordinate system $O_1X_1Y_1Z_1$; $A_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \psi(t) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\psi(t) & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ is transition matrix from coordinate system $O_1X_1Y_1Z_1$ to coordinate system $OXYZ$.

Denote the product of matrices through the matrix A

$$A = A_1A_2A_3A_4 = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11}A_{12}A_{13} \\ A_{21}A_{22}A_{23} \\ A_{31}A_{32}A_{33} \end{pmatrix}, \tag{3}$$

where the elements $A_{ij} (i,j=1,2,3)$ of this matrix will have the following forms:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11} &= 1 + \psi(t)\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1(t); & A_{12} &= -\mathcal{G}_1(t) + \mathcal{G}_1(t)\psi(t)\beta_0 + \psi(t)\gamma_0; & A_{13} &= -\beta_0\psi(t)\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1(t) + \psi(t); \\ A_{21} &= \mathcal{G}_1(t); & A_{22} &= 1; & A_{23} &= -\mathcal{G}_1(t)\beta_0 - \gamma_0; & A_{31} &= -\psi(t) + \gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1(t); & A_{32} &= \mathcal{G}_1(t)\psi(t) + \mathcal{G}_1(t)\beta_0 + \gamma_0; \\ & & & & & & A_{33} &= 1 - \beta_0\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1(t). \end{aligned}$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + \psi(t)\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1(t) & -\mathcal{G}_1(t) + \mathcal{G}_1(t)\psi(t)\beta_0 + \psi(t)\gamma_0 & -\beta_0\psi(t)\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1(t) + \psi(t) \\ \mathcal{G}_1(t) & 1 & -\mathcal{G}_1(t)\beta_0 - \gamma_0 \\ -\psi(t) + \gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1(t) & \mathcal{G}_1(t)\psi(t) + \mathcal{G}_1(t)\beta_0 + \gamma_0 & 1 - \beta_0\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1(t) \end{bmatrix} \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \psi(t) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\psi(t) & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}; & B_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -\beta_0 \\ 0 & 1 & -\gamma_0 \\ \beta_0 & \gamma_0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}; \\ B_3 &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\mathcal{G}_2(t) & 0 \\ \mathcal{G}_2(t) & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}; & B_4 &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \beta_0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\beta_0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

For the rear axle and rear wheels, the relations $A_{ij}^{(1)}(\beta_0, \mathcal{G}_1) = B_{ij}^{(2)}(-\beta_0, \mathcal{G}_2)$, $a_{ij}^{(1)}(\beta_0, \mathcal{G}_1) = b_{ij}^{(2)}(-\beta_0, \mathcal{G}_2)$, therefore, we will have:

$$\begin{aligned} B_{11} &= 1 + \psi(t)\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2(t); & B_{12} &= -\mathcal{G}_2(t) + \mathcal{G}_2(t)\psi(t)\beta_0 + \psi(t)\gamma_0; \\ B_{13} &= -\beta_0\psi(t)\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2(t) + \psi(t); & B_{21} &= \mathcal{G}_2(t); \\ B_{22} &= 1; & B_{23} &= -\mathcal{G}_2(t)\beta_0 - \gamma_0; & B_{31} &= -\psi(t) + \gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2(t); \\ B_{32} &= \mathcal{G}_2(t)\psi(t) + \mathcal{G}_2(t)\beta_0 + \gamma_0; & B_{33} &= 1 - \beta_0\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2(t); \\ B &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 + \psi(t)\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2(t) & -\mathcal{G}_2(t) - \mathcal{G}_2(t)\psi(t)\beta_0 + \psi(t)\gamma_0 & \beta_0\psi(t)\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2(t) + \psi(t) \\ \mathcal{G}_2(t) & 1 & \mathcal{G}_2(t)\beta_0 - \gamma_0 \\ -\psi(t) + \gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2(t) & \mathcal{G}_2(t)\psi(t) + \mathcal{G}_2(t)\beta_0 + \gamma_0 & 1 + \beta_0\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2(t) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Using formulas (1) - (5), we find:

$O(x_1, y_1, z_1)$ is center of mass of the front suspension

$$x_{01} = x - l_1\theta; \quad y_{01} = y + l_1; \quad z_{01} = z, \tag{6}$$

$B(x_2, y_2, z_2)$ is rear axle center of mass

$$x_{02} = x + l_2\theta; \quad y_{02} = y - l_2; \quad z_{02} = z, \tag{7}$$

$C_I(x_3, y_3, z_3)$ is center of mass of the front left wheel

$$x_{03}=x+(x_0+l_3A_{11}^{(1)})\theta-l_1\theta; y_{03}=y+(y_0-l_3A_{21}^{(1)})+l_1; z_{03}=z+(z_0+l_3A_{31}^{(1)}), \quad (8)$$

$C(x_4, y_4, z_4)$ is center of mass of front right wheel

$$x_{04}=x+(-x_0-l_3A_{11}^{(2)})\theta-l_1\theta; y_{04}=y+(-y_0+l_3A_{21}^{(2)})+l_1; z_{04}=z+(-z_0-l_3A_{31}^{(2)}), \quad (9)$$

$D_I(x_5, y_5, z_5)$ is center of mass of the rear left wheel

$$x_{05}=x+l_2\theta-L_1\theta; y_{05}=y-l_2-L_1; z_{05}=z, \quad (10)$$

$D(x_6, y_6, z_6)$ is center of mass of rear right wheel

$$x_{06}=x+l_2\theta+L_1\theta; y_{06}=y-l_2+L_1; z_{06}=z, \quad (11)$$

where the coordinates of the center of the left pin x_0, y_0, z_0 are

$$x_0=-l_*; y_0=0; z_0=l_*\psi. \quad (12)$$

Using formulas (6)-(12), we find the speeds of the center of mass of the front suspension V_1 , the rear axle V_2 and the four wheels of the car V_3, V_4, V_5, V_6 .

The speed of the center of mass of the front suspension: $V_1^2 = (\dot{x} - l_1\dot{\theta})^2 + \dot{y}^2 + \dot{z}^2$,

speed of the center of mass rear axle: $V_2^2 = (\dot{x} - l_2\dot{\theta})^2 + \dot{y}^2 + \dot{z}^2$,

speed of the center of mass of the front left wheel:

$$V_3^2 = \left(\dot{x} + l_3(\dot{\psi}\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1(t) + \psi(t)\gamma_0\dot{\mathcal{G}}_1)\theta(t) + (-l_* + l_3(1 + \psi(t)\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1(t) - l_1)\dot{\theta}) \right)^2 + \left((\dot{y} - l_3\dot{\mathcal{G}}_1) - (-l_3\mathcal{G}_1(t) + l_1)\theta(t)\dot{\theta} \right)^2 + \left((\dot{z} + l_*\dot{\psi}) + l_3(-\dot{\psi} + \gamma_0\dot{\mathcal{G}}_1) \right)^2,$$

speed of the center of mass of the front right wheel:

$$V_4^2 = \left(\dot{x} + l_3(\dot{\psi}\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2(t) + \psi(t)\gamma_0\dot{\mathcal{G}}_2)\theta(t) + (l_* - l_3(1 + \psi(t)\gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2(t) - l_1)\dot{\theta}) \right)^2 + \left((\dot{y} + l_3\dot{\mathcal{G}}_2) - (l_3\mathcal{G}_2(t) + l_1)\theta(t)\dot{\theta} \right)^2 + \left((\dot{z} - l_*\dot{\psi}) - l_3(-\dot{\psi} + \gamma_0\dot{\mathcal{G}}_2) \right)^2,$$

speed of the center of mass of the rear left wheel:

$$V_5^2 = \left(\dot{x} + l_2\dot{\theta} - (l_* + l_3)\theta(t)\dot{\theta} \right)^2 + \left(\dot{y} + l_2\theta(t)\dot{\theta} - (l_* + l_3)\dot{\theta} \right)^2 + \dot{z}^2,$$

speed of the center of mass of the rear right wheel:

$$V_6^2 = \left(\dot{x} + l_2\dot{\theta} - (l_* + l_3)\theta(t)\dot{\theta} \right)^2 + \left(\dot{y} + l_2\theta(t)\dot{\theta} + (l_* + l_3)\dot{\theta} \right)^2 + \dot{z}^2.$$

Let us now express the angles χ_i, θ_i of the wheels and the coordinates x_i, y_i ($i = \overline{1,4}$) through the generalized coordinates of the system. Here χ_i is the angle between the Oz axis and the median plane of the wheel, θ_i is the angle between the Oy axis and the trace of the median plane of the wheel on the road, x_i, y_i are the coordinates of the meeting point of the straight line of greatest inclination passing in the median plane of the wheel through its center with the plane XOY roads. According to matrix (4)

$$\begin{aligned} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \chi_1\right) &= A_{31}^{(1)} = \cos\beta_0 a_{31}^{(1)} + \sin\beta_0 a_{33}^{(1)}, \quad \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \chi_2\right) = B_{31}^{(2)} = \cos\beta_0 b_{31}^{(2)} - \sin\beta_0 b_{33}^{(2)}, \\ \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \chi_3\right) &= \sin\beta, \quad \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \chi_4\right) = \sin\beta, \quad \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_1\right) = A_{21}^{(1)} = \cos\beta_0 a_{21}^{(1)} + \sin\beta_0 a_{23}^{(1)}, \\ (13) \quad \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_2\right) &= B_{21}^{(2)} = \cos\beta_0 b_{21}^{(2)} - \sin\beta_0 b_{23}^{(2)}, \quad \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_3\right) = \sin\theta, \quad \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_4\right) = \sin\theta. \end{aligned}$$

From these relations we find (in a linear approximation):

$$\theta_1 = \theta + \mathcal{G}_1; \theta_2 = \theta + \mathcal{G}_2; \theta_3 = \theta_4 = \theta; \chi_1 = \psi - \gamma_0\mathcal{G}_1; \chi_2 = \psi - \gamma_0\mathcal{G}_2; \chi_3 = \beta; \chi_4 = -\beta. \quad (13')$$

The values x_i, y_i are related to the generalized coordinates as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= x_{03} - r_1 A_{31}^{(1)} = x + (-l\psi + l_3 A_{11}^{(1)})\theta - l_1\theta - r_1 A_{31}^{(1)}, \\ y_1 &= y_{03} - r_1 A_{32}^{(1)} = y - l_3 A_{21}^{(1)} + l_1 - r_1 A_{32}^{(1)}, \\ x_2 &= x_{04} - r_2 B_{31}^{(2)} = x + (l\psi - l_3 B_{11}^{(2)})\theta - l_1\theta - r_2 B_{31}^{(2)}, \\ y_2 &= y_{04} - r_2 B_{32}^{(2)} = y + l_3 B_{21}^{(2)} + l_1 - r_2 B_{32}^{(2)}, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned}x_3 &= x_{05} - r_3 \beta \theta = x + l_2 \theta - L_1 \theta - r_3 \beta \theta, \\y_3 &= y_{05} = y - l_2 - L_1 \theta, \\x_4 &= x_{06} + r_4 \beta \theta = x + l_2 \theta + L_1 \theta + r_4 \beta \theta, \\y_4 &= y_{06} = y - l_2 + L_1 \theta.\end{aligned}$$

To find the kinematics of the system, we determine $\Omega_{1x}, \Omega_{1y}, \Omega_{1z}$ components of the instantaneous angular velocity of the front left wheel along the coordinate axes, $\Omega_{2x}, \Omega_{2y}, \Omega_{2z}$ are components of the instantaneous angular velocity of the front right wheel along the coordinate axes, $\Omega_{3x}, \Omega_{3y}, \Omega_{3z}$ are components of the instantaneous angular velocity of the rear left wheel along the coordinate axes, $\Omega_{4x}, \Omega_{4y}, \Omega_{4z}$ are components of the instantaneous angular velocity of the rear right wheel along the coordinate axes.

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_{1x} &= -\dot{\Delta}_1 + \dot{\psi} \sin \vartheta_1 + \dot{\theta} A_{31}^{(1)} + \dot{\vartheta}_1 \sin \beta_0; & \Omega_{2x} &= -\dot{\Delta}_2 + \dot{\psi} \sin \vartheta_2 + \dot{\theta} A_{31}^{(2)} - \dot{\vartheta}_2 \sin \beta_0; \\ \Omega_{1y} &= \dot{\psi} \cos \vartheta_1 + \dot{\theta} A_{32}^{(1)}; & \Omega_{2y} &= \dot{\psi} \cos \vartheta_2 + \dot{\theta} A_{32}^{(2)}; \\ \Omega_{1z} &= \dot{\psi} A_{23}^{(1)} + \dot{\theta} A_{33}^{(1)} + \dot{\vartheta}_1 \cos \beta_0; & \Omega_{2z} &= \dot{\psi} A_{23}^{(2)} + \dot{\theta} A_{33}^{(2)} + \dot{\vartheta}_2 \cos \beta_0; \\ \Omega_{3x} &= -\dot{\Delta}_3 + \dot{\theta} \sin \beta; & \Omega_{4x} &= -\dot{\Delta}_4 - \dot{\theta} \sin \beta; \\ \Omega_{3y} &= 0; & \Omega_{4y} &= 0; \\ \Omega_{3z} &= \dot{\theta} \cos \beta; & \Omega_{4z} &= \dot{\theta} \cos \beta.\end{aligned}\tag{15}$$

Substituting the values $A_{ij}^{(1)}$ and $B_{ij}^{(2)}$ ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$) from (4) and (5) into (15), we find the values of the instantaneous angular velocities $\Omega_{ix}, \Omega_{iy}, \Omega_{iz}$ ($i = 1, \dots, 4$).

Expanding in (15) the cosine and sine functions in a series and leaving only linear terms, we get: components of the instantaneous angular velocity of the front left wheel:

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_{1x} &= -\dot{\Delta}_1 + \dot{\psi} \vartheta_1 + \dot{\theta}(-\psi + \gamma_0 \vartheta_1) + \dot{\vartheta}_1 \beta_0, \\ \Omega_{1y} &= \dot{\psi} + \dot{\theta}(\vartheta_1 \psi + \vartheta_1 \beta_0 + \gamma_0), \\ \Omega_{1z} &= \dot{\psi}(-\vartheta_1 \beta_0 - \gamma_0) + \dot{\theta}(1 - \beta_0 \gamma_0 \vartheta_1) + \dot{\vartheta}_1,\end{aligned}$$

components of the instantaneous angular velocity of the front right wheel:

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_{2x} &= -\dot{\Delta}_2 + \dot{\psi} \vartheta_2 + \dot{\theta}(-\psi + \gamma_0 \vartheta_2) - \dot{\vartheta}_2 \beta_0, \\ \Omega_{2y} &= \dot{\psi} + \dot{\theta}(\vartheta_2 \psi - \vartheta_2 \beta_0 + \gamma_0), \\ \Omega_{2z} &= \dot{\psi}(\vartheta_2 \beta_0 - \gamma_0) + \dot{\theta}(1 + \beta_0 \gamma_0 \vartheta_2) + \dot{\vartheta}_2,\end{aligned}$$

components of the instantaneous angular velocity of the rear left wheel:

$$\Omega_{3x} = -\dot{\Delta}_3 + \dot{\theta} \sin \beta, \quad \Omega_{3y} = 0, \quad \Omega_{3z} = \dot{\theta} \cos \beta,$$

components of the instantaneous angular velocity of the rear right wheel:

$$\Omega_{4x} = -\dot{\Delta}_4 - \dot{\theta} \sin \beta, \quad \Omega_{4y} = 0, \quad \Omega_{4z} = \dot{\theta} \cos \beta.$$

The dynamic system under consideration consists of 6 interconnected bodies: a front dependent suspension, the rear part of the car without the front wheel suspension, and four wheels. Therefore, the kinetic energy of the system is

$$T = \sum_{i=1}^6 T_i, \tag{16}$$

where T_1 is the kinetic energy of the front suspension, T_2 is the kinetic energy of the rear of the vehicle without the front suspension and wheels, T_3 is the kinetic energy of the front left wheel, T_4 is the kinetic energy of the front right wheel, T_5 is the kinetic energy of the rear left wheel, T_6 is the kinetic energy of the rear right wheel.

The expressions for kinetic energy are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}T_1 &= \frac{1}{2} m_3 V_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} B \dot{\psi}^2 + \frac{1}{2} B_1 \dot{\theta}^2, & T_2 &= \frac{1}{2} m_1 V_2^2 + \frac{1}{2} D \dot{\theta}^2, \\ T_3 &= \frac{1}{2} m_{21} V_3^2 + \frac{1}{2} C_1 \Omega_{1x}^2 + \frac{1}{2} A_1 (\Omega_{1y}^2 + \Omega_{1z}^2), \\ T_4 &= \frac{1}{2} m_{22} V_4^2 + \frac{1}{2} C_2 \Omega_{2x}^2 + \frac{1}{2} A_2 (\Omega_{2y}^2 + \Omega_{2z}^2),\end{aligned}\tag{17}$$

$$T_5 = \frac{1}{2} m_{23} V_5^2 + \frac{1}{2} m_{23} \Omega_{3x}^2 + \frac{1}{2} A_3 (\Omega_{3y}^2 + \Omega_{3z}^2),$$

$$T_6 = \frac{1}{2} m_{24} V_6^2 + \frac{1}{2} m_{24} \Omega_{4x}^2 + \frac{1}{2} A_4 (\Omega_{4y}^2 + \Omega_{4z}^2),$$

In accordance with König's theorem, we have $T_i = T_i' + T_i''$,

where T_i' is the kinetic energy of translational motion with the speed $\vec{V}_i$ of the center of mass of the system, and T_i'' is the kinetic energy of rotational motion with the instantaneous angular velocity $\vec{\Omega}_i$ of the system relative to its center of mass.

The kinetic energy of the front suspension:

$$T_1 = \frac{1}{2} m_3 \dot{x}^2 - m_3 l \dot{\theta} \dot{x} + \frac{1}{2} m_3 \dot{y}^2 + \frac{1}{2} m_3 \dot{z}^2 + \frac{1}{2} (m_3 l_1^2 + B_1) \dot{\theta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} B \dot{\psi}^2,$$

The rear axle kinetic energy:

$$T_2 = \frac{1}{2} m_1 \dot{x}^2 + m_1 \dot{x} l_2 \dot{\theta} + \frac{1}{2} m_1 \dot{y}^2 + \frac{1}{2} m_1 \dot{z}^2 + \frac{1}{2} (D + m_1 l_2^2) \dot{\theta}^2,$$

The kinetic energy of the front left wheel:

$$T_3 = \frac{1}{2} m_{21} \dot{x}^2 + (-m_{21} l_1 - m_{21} l_* + m_{21} l_3) \dot{\theta} \dot{x} + \frac{1}{2} m_{21} \dot{y}^2 + (-m_{21} l_3 \mathcal{G}_1(t) - m_{21} l_1 \theta(t) \dot{\theta}) \dot{y} +$$

$$\frac{1}{2} m_{21} \dot{z}^2 + ((m_{21} l_*^2 - m_{21} l_* l_3) \dot{\psi} + m_{21} l_3 \gamma_0 \dot{\mathcal{G}}_1) \dot{z} + \frac{1}{2} (-2m_{21} l_* l_3 + 2m_{21} l_* l_1 + A_1 - 2m_{21} l_3 l_1 + m_{21} l_1^2 +$$

$$+ m_{21} l_*^2 + m_{21} l_3^2) \dot{\theta}^2 + ((A_1 - A_1 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_1(t) - C_1 \psi(t) \beta_0 + m_{21} l_3 \theta(t) l_1 + C_1 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_1(t) \beta_0) \dot{\mathcal{G}}_1 +$$

$$+ C_1 \psi(t) - C_1 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_1(t) \dot{\Delta}_1) \dot{\theta} + \frac{1}{2} (A_1 + m_{21} l_*^2 - 2m_{21} l_* l_3 + m_{21} l_3^2 + 2A_1 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_1(t) \beta_0) \dot{\psi}^2 +$$

$$+ ((m_{21} l_* l_3 \gamma_0 - A_1 \gamma_0 - m_{21} l_3^2 \gamma_0 - A_1 \mathcal{G}_1(t) \beta_0 + C_1 \mathcal{G}_1(t) \beta_0) \dot{\mathcal{G}}_1 -$$

$$- C_1 \dot{\Delta}_1 \mathcal{G}_1(t) \dot{\psi} + \frac{1}{2} (A_1 + m_{22} l_3^2) \dot{\mathcal{G}}_1^2 - C_1 \dot{\Delta}_1 \dot{\mathcal{G}}_1 \beta_0 + \frac{1}{2} C_1 \dot{\Delta}_1^2),$$

The kinetic energy of the front right wheel:

$$T_4 = \frac{1}{2} m_{22} \dot{x}^2 + (m_{22} (l_* - l_3 - l_1) \dot{\theta}) \dot{x} + \frac{1}{2} m_{22} \dot{y}^2 + (-m_{22} l_3 \mathcal{G}_2(t) + l_1 \theta(t) \dot{\theta} +$$

$$m_{22} l_3 \dot{\mathcal{G}}_2(t)) \dot{y} + \frac{1}{2} m_{22} \dot{z}^2 + (m_{22} (-l_* + l_3) \dot{\psi} - m_{22} l_3 \gamma_0 \dot{\mathcal{G}}_2) \dot{z} + \frac{1}{2} (m_{22} l_*^2 -$$

$$+ 2m_{22} l_* l_3 - 2m_{22} l_* l_1 + m_{22} l_3^2 + 2m_{22} l_3 l_1 + m_{22} l_1^2 + A_2) \dot{\theta}^2 + ((C_2 \mathcal{G}_2(t) (-\psi(t) -$$

$$+ C_1 \psi(t) - C_1 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_1(t) \dot{\Delta}_1) \dot{\theta} + \frac{1}{2} (A_1 + m_{21} l_*^2 - 2m_{21} l_* l_3 + m_{21} l_3^2 + 2A_1 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_1(t) \beta_0) \dot{\psi}^2 +$$

$$- C_2 \dot{\Delta}_2 (-\psi(t) + \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_2(t)) \dot{\theta} + \frac{1}{2} A_2 (-2A_2 \beta_0 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_2(t) + m_{22} l_*^2 - 2m_{22} l_* l_3 +$$

$$+ m_{22} l_3^2) \dot{\psi}^2 + (m_{22} l_3 \gamma_0 (l_* - l_3) + A_2 (\mathcal{G}_2(t) \beta_0 \gamma_0) - C_2 \beta_0 \mathcal{G}_2(t) \dot{\mathcal{G}}_2 -$$

$$- C_2 \dot{\Delta}_2 \mathcal{G}_2(t)) \dot{\psi} + \frac{1}{2} (m_{22} l_3^2 + A_2) \dot{\mathcal{G}}_2^2 + C_2 \dot{\Delta}_2 \beta_0 \dot{\mathcal{G}}_2 + \frac{1}{2} C_2 \dot{\Delta}_2^2),$$

The kinetic energy of the rear left wheel:

$$T_5 = \frac{1}{2} m_{23} \dot{x}^2 + m_{23} (l_2 + (l_* + l_3) \theta(t) \dot{\theta}) \dot{x} + \frac{1}{2} m_{23} \dot{y}^2 + m_{23} (l_2 \theta(t) - l_* - l_3) \dot{\theta} \dot{y} +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} m_{23} \dot{z}^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2} m_{23} ((l_2 + (l_* + l_3) \theta(t))^2 + (l_2 \theta(t) - (l_* - l_3))^2 + \frac{C_3 \beta^2}{2}) \dot{\theta}^2 - C_3 \dot{\Delta}_3 \beta \dot{\theta} + \frac{1}{2} C_3 \dot{\Delta}_3^2, \right.$$

The kinetic energy of the rear right wheel:

$$T_6 = \frac{1}{2} m_{24} \dot{x}^2 + m_{24} (l_2 - (l_* + l_3) \theta(t) \dot{\theta}) \dot{x} + \frac{1}{2} m_{24} \dot{y}^2 + m_{24} (l_2 \theta(t) + l_* + l_3) \dot{\theta} \dot{y} + \frac{1}{2} m_{24} \dot{z}^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2} m_{24} ((l_2 - (l_* + l_3) \theta(t))^2 + (l_2 \theta(t) + (l_* + l_3))^2) + \frac{C_4 \beta^2}{2} \right) \dot{\theta}^2 + C_4 \dot{\Delta}_4 \beta \dot{\theta} + \frac{1}{2} C_4 \dot{\Delta}_4^2. \quad (18)$$

When compiling the equations of vehicle motion, taking into account the deformability of tires, one should take into account the kinematic relationships imposed on the rolling of the wheels [4]. We assume that the wheel is dynamically and geometrically symmetrical about its median plane. Consider the line obtained by the intersection of the middle plane of the undeformed tire. This line is called the center line of the wheel. When the wheel rolls on a horizontal plane with a deformable tire, the deformation of the center line is associated with the deformation of the entire tire. We will assume that tire deformations are sufficiently small. According to the theory of rolling of an elastic

$$\begin{aligned} & \dot{x}(\theta + \vartheta_i + \phi_i) - \dot{y} + \dot{\theta}((l_3 - l_* - l_1) \phi_i + (l_3 - l_* - l_1) \vartheta_i + (l_3 - l_*) \theta) + (r_i \theta + 2r_i \vartheta_i + r_i \phi_i) \dot{\psi} + \\ & + (r_i \beta_0 - r_i \gamma_0 \phi_i + r_i \psi + l_3 - r_i \gamma_0 \vartheta_i - r_i \gamma_0 \theta) \dot{\vartheta}_i + \dot{\xi}_i = 0, \\ & \dot{x} \beta_i (\phi_i - \alpha_i \xi_i) + \dot{\theta} (1 - (l_1 - l_3 + l_*) \beta_i \alpha_i \xi_i + (l_3 - l_* - l_1) \beta_i \phi_i^2) + \dot{\psi} \beta_i r_i (\phi_i - \alpha_i \xi_i) + \dot{\vartheta}_i (1 + \beta_i r_i \gamma_0 (\alpha_i \xi_i - \phi_i)) + \\ & + \dot{\phi}_i + \gamma_i \gamma_0 \vartheta_i - \gamma_i \psi = 0, \\ & \dot{x}(\mu_i r_i + 1 + \lambda_i \eta_i - \mu_i r_{oi}) + \dot{y}((r_i - r_{oi}) \mu_i \vartheta_i + (r_i - r_{oi}) \mu_i \theta + \dot{\theta}((l_3 - l_* - l_1 - l_1 \mu_i r_i + l_1 \mu_i r_{oi} + l_* \mu_i r_{oi} - \\ & - l_3 \mu_i r_{oi} + l_3 \mu_i r_i - l_* \mu_i r_i) + (l_3 - l_1 - l_*) \lambda_i \eta_i) + \\ & + \dot{\eta}_i + r_i \dot{\Delta}_i + ((-l_3 - r_i^2 \beta_0 \mu_i - l_3 \mu_i r_i + l_3 \mu_i r_{oi} - r_i \beta_0 + r_i \beta_0 \mu_i r_{oi}) \theta) + (-r_i^2 \beta_0 \mu_i + l_3 \mu_i r_{oi} \\ & + r_i \beta_0 \mu_i r_{oi} - l_3 \mu_i r_i - l_3 - r_i \beta_0) \vartheta_i - (r_i \gamma_0 \lambda_i) \eta_i - r_i^2 \gamma_0 \mu_i + r_i \gamma_0 \mu_i r_{oi} - r_i \gamma_0) \dot{\vartheta}_i = 0, \quad i = \overline{1, 4} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $\alpha_j, \beta_j, \gamma_j, \lambda_i, \nu_i$ are the kinematic parameters of the tire, χ_i is the angle between the perpendicular to the road and the middle plane of the wheel, ϕ_i is the angle between the tangent and the axis, which coincides with the trace of the center line of the wheel plane (tire twist angle), ξ_i is lateral displacement of the tire center line at a point coinciding with the stationary motion of the car with the support, η_i is the longitudinal deformation of the tire, θ is the angle between the Ox axis and the trace of the middle plane of the wheel on the road. The values x_i, y_i, θ, χ_i are expressed in terms

tire [5], due to the smallness of the tire deformation, we will consider the transverse, longitudinal, angular and radial deformations of the tire.

When the tire is deformed, a contact patch will be obtained, in which there is a whole segment of the center line. Further, from the assumption that the center of the contact area does not slip, the condition that the velocity is equal to zero for any point of this segment follows. In the case of curvilinear motion, the kinematic equations, which mean the conditions for wheel rolling without slip, with transverse and longitudinal deformation of tires have the form [6]

of generalized coordinates $q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n$. The values $\alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i, \nu_i, \lambda_i$ of the kinematic parameters are found experimentally.

The quantities $x_i, y_i, \chi_i, \theta_i$ are associated with generalized coordinates and are determined by formulas (13) and (14).

Substituting the values $x_i, y_i, A_{ij}^{(1)}, B_{ij}^{(2)}$, into (19), we obtain the kinematic equations for the motion of the car along a curvilinear path of sufficiently small curvature:

$$\begin{aligned} & \dot{x}(\theta + \vartheta_1 + \phi_1) - \dot{y} + \dot{\theta}((l_3 - l_* - l_1) \phi_1 + (l_3 - l_* - l_1) \vartheta_1 + (l_3 - l_*) \theta) + (r_1 \theta + 2r_1 \vartheta_1 + r_1 \phi_1) \dot{\psi} + \\ & + (r_1 \beta_0 - r_1 \gamma_0 \phi_1 + r_1 \psi + l_3 - r_1 \gamma_0 \vartheta_1 - r_1 \gamma_0 \theta) \dot{\vartheta}_1 + \dot{\xi}_1 = 0, \\ & \dot{x} \beta_1 (\phi_1 - \alpha_1 \xi_1) + \dot{\theta} (1 - (l_1 - l_3 + l_*) \beta_1 \alpha_1 \xi_1 + (l_3 - l_* - l_1) \beta_1 \phi_1^2) + \dot{\psi} \beta_1 r_1 (\phi_1 - \alpha_1 \xi_1) + \dot{\vartheta}_1 (1 + \beta_1 r_1 \gamma_0 (\alpha_1 \xi_1 - \phi_1)) + \\ & + \dot{\phi}_1 + \gamma_1 \gamma_0 \vartheta_1 - \gamma_1 \psi = 0, \\ & \dot{x}(\mu_1 r_1 + 1 + \lambda_1 \eta_1 - \mu_1 r_{o1}) + \dot{y}((r_1 - r_{o1}) \mu_1 \vartheta_1 + (r_1 - r_{o1}) \mu_1 \theta + \dot{\theta}((l_3 - l_* - l_1 - l_1 \mu_1 r_1 + l_1 \mu_1 r_{o1} + l_* \mu_1 r_{o1} - \\ & - l_3 \mu_1 r_{o1} + l_3 \mu_1 r_1 - l_* \mu_1 r_1) + (l_3 - l_1 - l_*) \lambda_1 \eta_1) + \dot{\eta}_1 + r_1 \dot{\Delta}_1 + ((-l_3 - r_1^2 \beta_0 \mu_1 - l_3 \mu_1 r_1 + l_3 \mu_1 r_{o1} - r_1 \beta_0 + r_1 \beta_0 \mu_1 r_{o1}) \theta) + \\ & (-r_1^2 \beta_0 \mu_1 + l_3 \mu_1 r_{o1} + r_1 \beta_0 \mu_1 r_{o1} - l_3 \mu_1 r_1 - l_3 - r_1 \beta_0) \vartheta_1 - (r_1 \gamma_0 \lambda_1) \eta_1 - r_1^2 \gamma_0 \mu_1 + r_1 \gamma_0 \mu_1 r_{o1} - r_1 \gamma_0) \dot{\vartheta}_1 = 0, \\ & \dot{x}(\theta + \vartheta_2 + \phi_2) - \dot{y} + \dot{\theta}((-l_3 + l_* - l_1) \phi_2 + (l_* - l_3 - l_1) \vartheta_2 + (l_* - l_3) \theta) + (r_2 \theta + 2r_2 \vartheta_2 - r_2 \psi \gamma_0 + r_2 \phi_2) \dot{\psi} + \\ & + (-r_2 \beta_0 - r_2 \gamma_0 \phi_2 + r_2 \psi - l_3 - 2r_2 \gamma_0 \vartheta_2 - r_2 \gamma_0 \theta) \dot{\vartheta}_2 + \dot{\xi}_2 = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \dot{x}\beta_2(\phi_2 - \alpha_2\xi_2) + \dot{\theta}(1 + (l_1 + l_3 - l_*)\beta_2\alpha_2\xi_2 - (l_3 + l_* - l_1)\beta_2\phi_2^2) + \\
& + \dot{\psi}\beta_2r_2(\phi_2 - \alpha_2\xi_2) + \dot{\vartheta}_2(1 + \beta_2r_2\gamma_0(\alpha_2\xi_2 - \phi_2)) + \dot{\phi}_2 + \gamma_2\gamma_0\vartheta_2 - \gamma_2\psi = 0, \\
& \dot{x}(1 + \mu_2r_2 + \lambda_2\eta_2 - \mu_2r_{o2}) + \dot{y}((\mu_2r_2 - \mu_2r_{o2})\vartheta_2 + (\mu_2r_2 - \mu_2r_{o2})\theta) + \dot{\theta}((l_1 - l_3 - l_1 - \\
& - l_1\mu_2r_2 + l_1\mu_2r_{o2} - ll\mu_2r_{o2} + l_3\mu_2r_{o2} - l_3\mu_2r_2 + ll\mu_2r_2) + (ll\lambda_2 - l_3\lambda_2 - l_1\lambda_2)\eta_2) + \\
& + \dot{\eta}_2 + r_2\dot{\Delta}_2 + ((l_3 - r_2^2\beta_0\mu_2 + l_3\mu_2r_2 - l_3\mu_2r_{o2} - r_2\beta_0 - r_2\beta_0\mu_2r_{o2})\theta) + (2r_2^2\beta_0\mu_2 + \\
& + l_3\mu_2r_{o2} - 2r_2\beta_0\mu_2r_{o2} + l_3\mu_2r_2 + l_3 + 2r_2\beta_0)\vartheta_2 - r_2\gamma_0\lambda_2\eta_2 - r_2^2\gamma_0\mu_2 + r_2\gamma_0\mu_2r_{o2} - r_2\gamma_0)\dot{\vartheta}_2 = 0, \\
& \dot{x}(\theta + \phi_3) - \dot{y} + \dot{\theta}((l_2 - r_3\beta)\phi_3 + (-l_2 - r_3\beta)\theta + (l_* + l_3)) + \dot{\xi}_3 = 0, \\
& \dot{x}\beta_3(\phi_3 - \alpha_3\xi_3) + \dot{\theta}((1 + \beta_3r_3\alpha_3 - \beta_3l_2\alpha_3)\xi_3 + (l_2 - r_3\beta)\beta_3\phi_3) - \gamma_3\beta + \dot{\phi}_3 = 0, \\
& \dot{x}(1 + \lambda_3\eta_3 + \mu_3r_3 - \mu_3r_{o3}) + \dot{y}((r_3 - r_{o3})\mu_3\theta) + \dot{\theta}((l_2 - r_3\beta + l_2\mu_3r_3 - \\
& l_2\mu_3r_{o3} - r_3^2\beta\mu_3 + r_3\beta\mu_3r_{o3}) + (l_2\lambda_3 - r_3\beta\lambda_3)\eta_3) + \dot{\eta}_3 + r_3\dot{\Delta}_3 = 0, \\
& \dot{x}(\theta + \phi_4) - \dot{y} + \dot{\theta}((l_2 - r_4\beta)\phi_4 + (-l_2 - r_4\beta)\theta + (-l_* - l_3)) + \dot{\xi}_4 = 0, \\
& \dot{x}\beta_4(\phi_4 - \alpha_4\xi_4) + \dot{\theta}((1 - \beta_4l_2\alpha_2 + \beta_4r_4\beta\alpha_4)\xi_4 + (l_2 - r_4\beta)\beta_4\phi_4) + \gamma_4\beta + \dot{\phi}_4 = 0, \\
& \dot{x}(1 + \lambda_4\eta_4 + \mu_4r_4 - \mu_4r_{o4}) + \dot{y}((r_4 - r_{o4})\mu_4\theta) + \dot{\theta}((l_2 - r_4\beta + l_2\mu_4r_4 - \\
& l_2\mu_4r_{o4} - r_4^2\beta\mu_4 + r_4\beta\mu_4r_{o4}) + (l_2\lambda_4 - r_4\beta\lambda_4)\eta_4) + \dot{\eta}_4 + r_4\dot{\Delta}_4 = 0,
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Within the framework of the phenomenological theory, we describe the equations for the forces and moments acting from the side of the road on the deformable wheel. All forces are divided into potential, which appear due to the elasticity of the tire, and non-potential, associated with friction in the tire material.

According to the theory of motion of rolling systems, the forces acting on the i -th wheel are equivalent to the transverse force F_i and the longitudinal force P_i

applied to the point K_i , M_{θ_i} is the moment about the vertical axis z , M_{x_i} is the moment about the longitudinal horizontal axis y and M_i is the moment about the transverse axis x .

The resulting moments and forces acting on the i -th wheel with transverse tire deformation have the form [6]:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \chi_i = (\psi(t) - \gamma_0\vartheta_i(t)); \dot{\chi}_i = \dot{\psi} - \gamma_0\dot{\vartheta}_i; \dot{\phi}_i = (\eta_{1i}(t)\dot{\xi}_i - (\eta_{2i}(t)\dot{\psi} - \gamma_0\dot{\vartheta}_i)); \\
& F_{xi} = a_i\xi_i + h_{1i}\dot{\xi}_i + \sigma_i N_i \chi_i + h_{2i}\dot{\chi}_i, \\
& M_{yi} = -\sigma_i N_i \xi_i - h_{3i}\dot{\xi}_i - \rho_i N_i \chi_i - h_{4i}\dot{\chi}_i, \\
& M_{theta_i} = \eta_{1i} b_i \xi_i' - \eta_{1i} b_i (\psi(t) - \gamma_0\vartheta_i(t)) + h_{5i} \dot{\phi}_i \quad (i = \overline{1, 4}).
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

The resulting moments and forces acting on the i -th wheel during the longitudinal deformation of the tires are determined by the expressions: $r_{shi} = r_{oi} - r_i$,

$$\begin{aligned}
& Fz_i = -Kr_1(r_{oi} - r_i) - h_{6i}(r_{oi} - r_i), \\
& F_{yi} = K_{\tau_i}\eta_i - N_i^m(a_{F_i} + b_{F_i}|\dot{y}_i|^n)\text{sign}\dot{y}_i,
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

$$M_{xi} = \mu_i N_i \eta_i + N_i^m(a_{M_i} + b_{M_i}|\dot{y}_i|^n)\text{sign}\dot{y}_i, \quad m \in [1; 2]; \quad n \in [2; 3], \quad (i = \overline{1, 4}).$$

where $a_i, b_i, h_i, k_i, a_{F_i}, b_{F_i}, a_{M_i}, b_{M_i}, \sigma_i, \rho_i, \mu_i$ coefficients are determined experimentally $r'_i = r_{oi} - r_i$.

The generalized forces are calculated by the formula

$$2R_j = \sum_{i=1}^m \left(F_i \frac{\partial x_i}{\partial q_j} + M_{\theta_i} \frac{\partial \theta_i}{\partial q_j} + M_{x_i} \frac{\partial \chi_i}{\partial q_j} + M_i \frac{\partial \vartheta_i}{\partial q_j} + P_i \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial q_j} \right),$$

or in our case

$$R_j = \sum_{i=1}^{11} \left[(F_i \sin \theta_i - P_i \cos \theta_i) \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial q_j} + (P_i \sin \theta_i - F_i \cos \theta_i) \frac{\partial x_i}{\partial q_j} + \right.$$

$$+ (N_i + F_{z_i}) \frac{\partial z_i}{\partial q_j} + M_{\theta_i} \frac{\partial \theta_i}{\partial q_j} + M_{\chi_i} \frac{\partial \chi_i}{\partial q_j} + (r_i P_i + M_i) \frac{\partial \Delta_i}{\partial q_j} \Big], \quad (23)$$

where $F_i = F_{x_i}$, $P_i = P_{y_i}$, $M_{\theta_i} = M_{z_i}$, $M_{\chi_i} = M_{y_i}$, $M_i = M_{x_i}$.

The components of the generalized forces on the x , y , z , θ , ψ , ϑ_1 , ϑ_2 , Δ_1 , Δ_2 , Δ_3 , Δ_4 axes have the form:

$$\begin{aligned} R_x &= F_1 \cos \theta_1 + F_2 \cos \theta_2 + (F_3 + F_4) \cos \theta - P_1 \sin \theta_1 - P_2 \sin \theta_2 - (P_3 + P_4) \sin \theta, \\ R_y &= F_1 \sin \theta_1 + F_2 \sin \theta_2 + (F_3 + F_4) \sin \theta + P_1 \cos \theta_1 + P_2 \cos \theta_2 + (P_3 + P_4) \cos \theta, \\ R_z &= \sum_{i=1}^4 N_i + \sum_{i=1}^4 F_{z_i}, \\ R_\theta &= \sum_{i=1}^4 M_{z_i} - (F_1 \cos \theta_1 + F_2 \cos \theta_2) \ell_1 + (F_3 + F_4) \ell_2 + (F_2 \sin \theta_2 - \\ &\quad - F_1 \sin \theta_1) \ell + (P_2 \cos \theta_2 - P_1 \cos \theta_1) \ell + (P_2 \sin \theta_2 - P_1 \sin \theta_1) \ell_1 + (P_4 - P_3) L, \\ R_\psi &= -(r_1 F_1 \cos \theta_1 + r_2 F_2 \cos \theta_2 - r_1 P_1 \sin \theta_1 - r_2 P_2 \sin \theta_2) \cos \beta_0 \cos \gamma_0 - \\ &\quad - (r_3 F_3 + r_4 F_4) \cos \beta + M_{y_1} \cos \theta_1 + M_{y_2} \cos \theta_2 + \sum_{i=3}^4 M_{y_i}, \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

$$R_{\vartheta_1} = M_{z_1} \cos \beta_0 \cos \gamma_0 - M_{x_1} \sin \beta_0 + P_1 e_1 \cos \beta_0 \sin \gamma_0,$$

$$R_{\vartheta_2} = M_{z_2} \cos \beta_0 \cos \gamma_0 + M_{x_2} \sin \beta_0 + P_2 e_2 \cos \beta_0 \sin \gamma_0,$$

$$R_{\Delta_1} = M_{n_1} = -r_1 P_1 + M_{x_1},$$

$$R_{\Delta_2} = M_{n_2} = -r_2 P_2 + M_{x_2},$$

$$R_{\Delta_3} = M_{n_3} = -r_3 P_3 \cos \beta + M_{x_3} \cos \beta,$$

$$R_{\Delta_4} = M_{n_4} = -r_4 P_4 \cos \beta + M_{x_4} \cos \beta,$$

where e_1 , e_2 are distances of the left and right front wheels, respectively, $\theta_1 = \theta + \vartheta_1$, $\theta_2 = \theta + \vartheta_2$,

Substituting the values $\theta_1 = \theta + \vartheta_1$, $\theta_2 = \theta + \vartheta_2$, $F_i = F_{x_i}$, $P_i = P_{y_i}$, $M_{\theta_i} = M_{z_i}$, $M_{\chi_i} = M_{y_i}$, $M_i = M_{x_i}$ ($i = \overline{1,4}$) into (21), (22) and (24), we obtain expressions for the generalized reaction forces acting on the wheels from the bearing surface.

The generalized forces $S_j = (q, \dot{q}, t)$, ($j = \overline{1, 11}$) acting on the system under consideration, in the calculation of which all forces are taken into account, except for the tire deformation forces associated with χ_i , φ_i angles and ξ_i , η_i displacements, already taken into account when searching for the expression R_j , ($j = \overline{1, 11}$), have the form:

$$\begin{aligned} S_\psi &= -k_1 \psi - h_1 \dot{\psi}, & S_{\vartheta_1} &= -k_2^{(1)} \vartheta_1 - h_2^{(1)} \dot{\vartheta}_1, \\ S_z &= -k_3 z - h_3 \dot{z}, & S_{\vartheta_2} &= -k_2^{(2)} \vartheta_2 - h_2^{(2)} \dot{\vartheta}_2, \\ S_\theta &= S_{\Delta_1} = S_{\Delta_2} = S_{\Delta_3} = S_{\Delta_4} = S_x = S_y = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where $k_1 = k_1' + C_{pc} \frac{L_{pc}^2}{2} + C_{uu} \frac{4L^2}{2}$ is angular stiffness of the system along the coordinate ψ , $k_2^{(1)}$, $k_2^{(2)}$, k_3 are angular rigidity along the coordinates ϑ_1 , ϑ_2 and z , $h_1 = h_{uu} \frac{4L^2}{2} + h_{pc} \frac{4L_{pc}^2}{2} + (h_{acac} + h_{aom}) \frac{4L_a^2}{4} + h_c$ is coefficient of viscous friction along the coordinate ψ , $h_2^{(1)}$, $h_2^{(2)}$, h_3 are coefficients of viscous friction along the coordinates ϑ_1 , ϑ_2 , z ; k_1' is the angular stiffness of the rod device, C_{pc} is the coefficient of elasticity of the spring, C_{uu} is the radial stiffness of the tire, L_{pc} is the distance from the center of mass of the system to the spring, h_{uu} , h_{pc} , h_a are the internal resistance of the tire, springs and shock absorber, h_c is the coefficient of viscous friction of the rod device. We assume that, within the limits of the change in generalized coordinates, the damping in the system has linear characteristics.

The equations of motion of the vehicle on m wheels, according to the theory of motion of rolling systems [6], are written as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{q}_j} - \frac{\partial T}{\partial q_j} = S_j + R_j \quad (j = \overline{1, 11}) \quad (26)$$

where S_j are the generalized forces acting on the system, R_j are the generalized forces due to the deformation of the pneumatics, T is the kinetic energy of the system under consideration,

$q_1 = x$, $q_2 = y$, $q_3 = z$, $q_4 = \theta$, $q_5 = \psi$, $q_6 = \mathcal{Q}_1$, $q_7 = \mathcal{Q}_2$, $q_8 = \Delta_1$, $q_9 = \Delta_2$, $q_{10} = \Delta_3$, $q_{11} = \Delta_4$ are generalized system coordinates.

Substituting the found values T , $S_{\Delta_x}, \dots, S_{\Delta_4}$ and R_j ($j = \overline{1, 11}$) into equations (26) and leaving only the linear terms, we obtain the equations for the dynamics of the curvilinear motion of the car:

$$\begin{aligned} m\ddot{x} + \alpha_4\ddot{\theta} - h_{21}\dot{\psi} + \gamma_0 h_{21}\dot{\mathcal{Q}}_1 + \gamma_0 h_{22}\dot{\mathcal{Q}}_2 + 2\sigma_1 N_1 \psi + 2\sigma_2 N_2 \psi - \sigma_1 N_1 \gamma_0 \mathcal{Q}_1 - \sigma_2 N_2 \gamma_0 \mathcal{Q}_2 + \\ + h_{11}\dot{\xi}_1 + h_{12}\dot{\xi}_2 + h_{13}\dot{\xi}_3 + h_{14}\dot{\xi}_4 + a_1 \xi_1 + a_2 \xi_2 + a_3 \xi_3 + a_4 \xi_4 = 0, \\ m\ddot{y} + \beta_4\ddot{\theta} - m_{21} l_3 \ddot{\mathcal{Q}}_1 + m_{22} l_3 \ddot{\mathcal{Q}}_2 - \sigma_3 N_3 \beta \theta + \sigma_4 N_4 \beta \theta - \sigma_3 N_3 \beta \mathcal{Q}_1 + \sigma_4 N_4 \beta \mathcal{Q}_2 + \\ + K_{\tau_1} \eta_1 + K_{\tau_2} \eta_2 + K_{\tau_3} \eta_3 + K_{\tau_4} \eta_4 = 0, \\ m\ddot{z} + \gamma_5 \dot{\psi} + \gamma_0 m_{21} l_3 \ddot{\mathcal{Q}}_1 - \gamma_0 m_{22} l_3 \ddot{\mathcal{Q}}_2 - K_{r_1} r_1 - h_{61} r_1 - K_{r_2} r_2 - \\ - h_{62} r_2 - K_{r_3} r_3 - h_{63} r_3 - K_{r_4} r_4 - h_{64} r_4 + K_{r_1} r_{o1} + h_{61} r_{o1} + K_{r_2} r_{o2} + \\ + h_{62} r_{o2} + K_{r_3} r_{o3} + h_{63} r_{o3} + K_{r_4} r_{o4} + h_{64} r_{o4} - N_1 - N_2 - N_3 - N_4 + k_3 z + h_3 \dot{z} = 0, \\ m_1 \ddot{x} + m_2 \ddot{y} + m_4 \ddot{\theta} + A_1 \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_1 + A_2 \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_2 - \beta C_3 \ddot{\Delta}_3 + \beta C_4 \ddot{\Delta}_4 + (l_1 h_{21} + l_2 h_{22} + l_3 h_{21} + l_4 h_{22}) \dot{\psi} - \\ + (l_1 - l_3 + l_*) \gamma_0 h_{21} \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_1 + (l_1 - l_3 - l_*) \gamma_0 h_{22} \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_2 + h_{11} l_1 \dot{\xi}_1 + h_{12} l_1 \dot{\xi}_2 + \\ + h_{13} l_2 \dot{\xi}_3 + h_{14} l_2 \dot{\xi}_4 - (\sigma_1 N_1 l_1 + \sigma_2 N_2 l_* + \sigma_1 N_1 l_3 - \sigma_2 N_2 l_1 - \sigma_1 N_1 l_* - \sigma_2 N_2 l_3) \psi + (\sigma_4 N_4 l_3 \beta + \\ + \sigma_4 N_4 l_* \beta + \sigma_3 N_3 l_3 \beta + \sigma_3 N_3 l_* \beta + \sigma_1 N_1 l_1 \gamma_0 + \sigma_1 N_1 l_* \gamma_0 - \sigma_1 N_1 l_3 \gamma_0) \mathcal{Q}_1 + (\sigma_2 N_2 l_1 \gamma_0 - \\ - \sigma_2 N_2 l_* \gamma_0 + \sigma_2 N_2 l_3 \gamma_0) \mathcal{Q}_2 + 2(\sigma_4 N_4 l_3 + \sigma_4 N_4 l_* + \sigma_3 N_3 l_3 + \sigma_3 N_3 l_*) \beta \theta - \eta_{24} b_4 \beta + \\ + \eta_{23} b_3 \beta - a_1 \xi_1 l_1 + a_1 \xi_1 l_* - a_1 \xi_1 l_3 - a_2 \xi_2 l_1 + a_2 \xi_2 l_* + a_4 \xi_4 l_2 - a_3 \xi_3 r_3 \beta - a_4 \xi_4 r_4 \beta + \sigma_4 N_4 r_4 - \\ - \sigma_3 N_3 r_3 + \sigma_3 N_3 \beta l_2 - \sigma_4 N_4 \beta l_2 - K \tau_3 \eta_3 l_* - K \tau_3 \eta_3 l_3 + K \tau_4 \eta_4 l_3 + K \tau_4 \eta_4 l_* = 0, \\ m_3 \ddot{z} + m_5 \dot{\psi} + \gamma_0 m_6 \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_1 + \gamma_0 m_7 \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_2 + (r_1 h_{21} + r_2 h_{22} + h_{42} + h_{41}) \dot{\psi} + (h_{21} r_1 - h_{41}) \gamma_0 \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_1 - (h_{22} r_2 - \\ - h_{42}) \gamma_0 \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_2 + h_{11} r_1 \dot{\xi}_1 + h_{12} r_2 \dot{\xi}_2 + h_{31} \dot{\xi}_1 + h_{32} \dot{\xi}_2 + a_1 \xi_1 r_1 + a_2 \xi_2 r_2 + (\sigma_1 N_1 r - \sigma_2 N_2 r_2 + r_{o1} N_1) \psi - \\ - (\sigma_1 r_1 - r_{o1}) \gamma_0 N_1 \mathcal{Q}_1 - (\sigma_2 r_2 - r_{o2}) N_2 \gamma_0 \mathcal{Q}_2 + k_1 \psi + h_1 \dot{\psi} = 0, \\ l_5 \ddot{y} + l_6 \ddot{z} + A \ddot{\theta} + l_7 \dot{\psi} + l_8 \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_1 - \beta_0 C_1 \ddot{\Delta}_1 - (h_{41} - h_{21} r_1) \gamma_0 \dot{\psi} - (h_{31} - h_{11} r_1) \gamma_0 \dot{\xi}_1 - \\ - (K \tau_1 r_1 \eta_1 - \gamma_0 r_{o1} N_1) \psi - (\sigma_1 N_1 - a_1 r_1) \gamma_0 \xi_1 - (K \tau_1 r_1 \beta_0 - K \tau_1 l_3) \eta_1 + k_2^{(1)} \mathcal{Q}_1 + h_2^{(1)} \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_1 = 0, \\ l_{55} \ddot{y} - l_{66} \ddot{z} + A_2 \ddot{\theta} + l_{77} \dot{\psi} + l_{88} \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_2 - \beta_0 C_2 \ddot{\Delta}_2 - (h_{42} - h_{22} r_2) \gamma_0 \dot{\psi} - (h_{32} - h_{12} r_2) \gamma_0 \dot{\xi}_2 + \\ + (r_{o2} - \sigma_2 r_2) N_2 \gamma_0 \psi - (\sigma_2 N_2 - a_2 r_2) \gamma_0 \xi_2 - (K \tau_2 r_2 \beta_0 - K \tau_2 l_3) \eta_2 + k_2^{(2)} \mathcal{Q}_2 + h_2^{(2)} \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_2 = 0, \\ C_1 (-\beta_0 \ddot{\mathcal{Q}}_1 + \ddot{\Delta}_1) - (r_1 K_{\tau_1} - \mu_1 N_1) \eta_1 = 0, \quad C_2 (\beta_0 \ddot{\mathcal{Q}}_2 + \ddot{\Delta}_2) - (r_2 K_{\tau_2} - \mu_2 N_2) \eta_2 = 0, \\ C_3 (-\beta_0 \ddot{\mathcal{Q}}_3 + \ddot{\Delta}_3) - (r_3 K_{\tau_3} - \mu_3 N_3) \eta_3 = 0, \quad C_4 (\beta_0 \ddot{\mathcal{Q}}_4 + \ddot{\Delta}_4) - (r_4 K_{\tau_4} - \mu_4 N_4) \eta_4 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

where the coefficients of the differential equations are expressed in terms of the design parameters of the system.

Introducing the notation

$$\begin{aligned} w_1 = \ddot{x}, \quad w_2 = \ddot{y}, \quad w_3 = \ddot{z}, \quad w_4 = \ddot{\theta}, \quad w_5 = \ddot{\psi}, \quad w_6 = \ddot{\mathcal{Q}}_1, \quad w_7 = \ddot{\mathcal{Q}}_2, \quad w_8 = \ddot{\Delta}_1, \quad w_9 = \ddot{\Delta}_2, \quad w_{10} = \ddot{\Delta}_3, \quad w_{11} = \ddot{\Delta}_4, \\ a_1 = \dot{x}, \quad a_2 = \dot{y}, \quad a_3 = \dot{z}, \quad a_4 = \dot{\theta}, \quad a_5 = \dot{\psi}, \quad a_6 = \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_1, \quad a_7 = \dot{\mathcal{Q}}_2, \quad a_8 = \dot{\Delta}_1, \quad a_9 = \dot{\Delta}_2, \quad a_{10} = \dot{\Delta}_3, \quad a_{11} = \dot{\Delta}_4. \end{aligned}$$

We find the equations of the dynamics of the curvilinear motion of the car, taking into account the elasticity and deformability of tires:

$$\begin{aligned}
&mw_1 + \alpha_4 w_4 - h_{21} w_5 + \gamma_0 h_{21} w_6 + \gamma_0 h_{22} w_7 + 2\sigma_1 N_1 \psi + 2\sigma_2 N_2 \psi - \sigma_1 N_1 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_1 - \sigma_2 N_2 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_2 + \\
&+ h_{11} \dot{\xi}_1 + h_{12} \dot{\xi}_2 + h_{13} \dot{\xi}_3 + h_{14} \dot{\xi}_4 + a_1 \xi_1 + a_2 \xi_2 + a_3 \xi_3 + a_4 \xi_4 = 0. \\
&mw_2 + \beta_4 w_4 - m_{21} l_3 w_6 + m_{22} l_3 w_7 - \sigma_3 N_3 \beta \theta + \sigma_4 N_4 \beta \theta - \sigma_3 N_3 \beta \mathcal{G}_1 + \sigma_4 N_4 \beta \mathcal{G}_2 + \\
&+ K_{r_1} \eta_1 + K_{r_2} \eta_2 + K_{r_3} \eta_3 + K_{r_4} \eta_4 = 0. \\
&mw_3 + \gamma_5 w_5 + \gamma_0 m_{21} l_3 w_6 - \gamma_0 m_{22} l_3 w_7 - K_{r_1} r_1 - h_{61} r_1 - K_{r_2} r_2 - h_{62} r_2 - K_{r_3} r_3 - h_{63} r_3 - K_{r_4} r_4 - \\
&- h_{64} r_4 + K_{r_1} r_{o1} + h_{61} r_{o1} + K_{r_2} r_{o2} + h_{62} r_{o2} + K_{r_3} r_{o3} + h_{63} r_{o3} + K_{r_4} r_{o4} + h_{64} r_{o4} - N_1 - N_2 - N_3 - N_4 + k_3 z + h_3 \dot{z} = 0. \\
&m_1 w_1 + m_2 w_2 + m_4 w_4 + A_1 w_6 + A_2 w_7 - \beta C_3 w_{10} + \beta C_4 w_{11} + (l_1 h_{21} + l_* h_{22} + l_3 h_{21} + l_* h_{21} + l_1 h_{22}) a_5 - \\
&+ (l_1 - l_3 + l_*) \gamma_0 h_{21} a_6 + (l_1 - l_3 - l_*) \gamma_0 h_{22} a_7 + h_{11} l_1 \dot{\xi}_1 + h_{12} l_1 \dot{\xi}_2 + \\
&+ h_{13} l_2 \dot{\xi}_3 + h_{14} l_2 \dot{\xi}_4 - (\sigma_1 N_1 l_1 + \sigma_2 N_2 l_* + \sigma_1 N_1 l_3 - \sigma_2 N_2 l_1 - \sigma_1 N_1 l_* - \sigma_2 N_2 l_3) \psi + (\sigma_4 N_4 l_3 \beta + \\
&+ \sigma_4 N_4 l_* \beta + \sigma_3 N_3 l_3 \beta + \sigma_3 N_3 l_* \beta + \sigma_3 N_3 l_3 \beta + \sigma_3 N_3 l_* \beta + \sigma_1 N_1 l_1 \gamma_0 + \sigma_1 N_1 l_* \gamma_0 - \sigma_1 N_1 l_3 \gamma_0) \mathcal{G}_1 + \sigma_2 N_2 \gamma_0 (l_1 - \\
&- l_* + l_3) \mathcal{G}_2 + (2\sigma_4 N_4 l_3 \beta_0 + 2\sigma_4 N_4 l_* \beta_0 + 2\sigma_3 N_3 l_3 \beta_0 + 2\sigma_3 N_3 l_* \beta_0) \theta - \eta_{24} b_4 \beta + \\
&+ \eta_{23} b_3 \beta - a_1 \xi_1 l_1 + a_1 \xi_1 l_3 - a_1 \xi_1 l_* - a_2 \xi_2 l_1 + a_2 \xi_2 l_* + a_4 \xi_4 l_2 - a_3 \xi_3 r_3 \beta - a_4 \xi_4 r_4 \beta + \sigma_4 N_4 r_4 - \\
&- \sigma_3 N_3 r_3 + \sigma_3 N_3 \beta l_2 - \sigma_4 N_4 \beta l_2 - K \tau a_3 \eta_3 l_* - K \tau a_3 \eta_3 l_3 + K \tau a_4 \eta_4 l_3 + K \tau a_4 \eta_4 l_* = 0. \\
&m_3 w_3 + m_5 w_5 + \gamma_0 m_6 w_6 + \gamma_0 m_7 w_7 + (r_1 h_{21} + r_2 h_{22} + h_{42} + h_{41}) a_5 + (h_{21} r_1 - h_{41}) \gamma_0 a_6 - (h_{22} r_2 - \\
&- h_{42}) \gamma_0 a_7 + h_{11} \dot{\xi}_1 r_1 + h_{12} \dot{\xi}_2 r_2 + h_{31} \dot{\xi}_1 + h_{32} \dot{\xi}_2 + a_1 \xi_1 r_1 + a_2 \xi_2 r_2 + (\sigma_1 N_1 r - \sigma_2 N_2 r_2 + r_{o1} N_1) \psi - \\
&- (\sigma_1 r_1 - r_{o1}) N_1 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_1 - (\sigma_2 r_2 - r_{o2}) N_2 \gamma_0 \mathcal{G}_2 + k_1 \psi + h_1 \dot{\psi} = 0. \\
&l_5 w_2 + l_6 w_3 + A w_4 + l_7 w_5 + l_8 w_6 - \beta_0 C_1 w_8 - (h_{41} - h_{21} r_1) \gamma_0 a_5 - (h_{31} - h_{11} r_1) \gamma_0 \dot{\xi}_1 - \\
&- (K \tau a_1 r_1 \eta_1 - \gamma_0 r_{o1} N_1) \psi - (\sigma_1 N_1 - a_1 r_1) \gamma_0 \xi_1 - (K \tau a_1 r_1 \beta_0 - K \tau a_1 l_3) \eta_1 + k_2^{(1)} \mathcal{G}_1 + h_2^{(1)} \dot{\mathcal{G}}_1 = 0. \\
&l_{55} w_2 - l_{66} w_3 + A_2 w_4 + l_{77} w_5 + l_{88} w_7 - \beta_0 C_2 w_9 - (h_{42} - h_{22} r_2) \gamma_0 a_5 - (h_{32} - h_{12} r_2) \gamma_0 \dot{\xi}_2 + \\
&+ (r_{o2} - \sigma_2 r_2) N_2 \gamma_0 \psi - (\sigma_2 N_2 - a_2 r_2) \gamma_0 \xi_2 - (K \tau a_2 r_2 \beta_0 - K \tau a_2 l_3) \eta_2 + k_2^{(2)} \mathcal{G}_2 + h_2^{(2)} \dot{\mathcal{G}}_2 = 0. \\
&C_1 (-\beta_0 w_6 + w_8) - (r_1 K_{r_1} - \mu_1 N_1) \eta_1 = 0. \quad C_2 (\beta_0 w_7 + w_9) - (r_2 K_{r_2} - \mu_2 N_2) \eta_2 = 0. \\
&C_3 (-\beta_0 w_4 + w_{10}) - (r_3 K_{r_3} - \mu_3 N_3) \eta_3 = 0. \quad C_4 (\beta_0 w_4 + w_{11}) - (r_4 K_{r_4} - \mu_4 N_4) \eta_4 = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

where, have the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
m &= m_3 + m_1 + m_{21} + m_{23} + m_{22} + m_{24}; \\
\alpha_4 &= -m_{22} l_3 + m_{21} l_3 + m_{23} l_2 + m_{24} l_2 - m_{22} l_1 + m_{22} l_* + m_1 l_2 - m_3 l_1 - m_{21} l_*; \\
\beta_4 &= m_{24} l_3 + m_{24} l_* - m_{23} l_* - m_{23} l_3; \quad \gamma_5 = -m_{22} l_* + m_{21} l_* + m_{22} l_3 - m_{21} l_3; \\
m_4 &= D + 2A_1 + A_2 + A_3 - 2m_{21} l_3 l_1 + A_4 + 2m_{22} l_3 l_1 + C_3 - 2m_{21} l_* l_3 - 2m_{22} l_* l_3 + C_4 + \\
&+ m_{22} l_*^2 + m_{21} l_*^2 + m_{21} l_3^2 + m_{22} l_3^2 + 2m_{24} l_* l_3 + 2m_{23} l_* l_3 - 2m_{22} l_* l_1 + 2m_{21} l_* l_1 + \\
&+ m_{23} l_3^2 + m_{24} l_3^2 + m_{24} l_*^2 + m_{23} l_2^2 + m_1 l_2^2 + m_3 l_1^2 + m_{23} l_*^2 + m_{21} l_1^2 + m_{24} l_2^2 + m_{22} l_1^2; \\
m_1 &= -m_{22} l_3 + m_{21} l_3 + m_{23} l_2 + m_{24} l_2 - m_{22} l_1 - m_{21} l_1 + m_{22} l_* + m_1 l_2 - m_3 l_1 - m_{21} l_*; \\
m_2 &= m_{24} l_3 + m_{24} l_* - m_{23} l_* - m_{23} l_3; \quad m_3 = -m_{22} l_* + m_{21} l_* + m_{22} l_3 - m_{21} l_3; \\
m_5 &= m_{22} l_3^2 + m_{21} l_3^2 + m_{22} l_*^2 + A_1 + B - 2m_{22} l_* l_3 + m_{21} l_*^2 - 2m_{21} l_* l_3 + A_2; \\
m_6 &= -m_{21} l_3^2 - A_1 + m_{21} l_* l_3; \quad m_7 = m_{22} l_3 l_* - m_{22} l_3^2 - A_2; \\
l_5 &= -m_{21} l_3; \quad l_6 = m_{21} l_3 \gamma_0; \quad l_7 = -m_{21} l_3^2 \gamma_0 - A_1 + m_{21} l_* l_3 \gamma_0; \quad l_8 = A_1 + m_{21} l_3^2; \\
l_{55} &= (m_{22} l_3); \quad l_{66} = m_{22} l_3 \gamma_0; \quad l_{77} = (m_{22} l_3 l_* - m_{22} l_3^2 - A_2) \gamma_0; \quad l_{88} = A_2 + m_{22} l_3^2;
\end{aligned}$$

Equations (20) and (27) describe the motion of the representative point in the thirty-four-dimensional phase space

$$(x, y, z, \dot{x}, \dot{y}, \dot{z}, \theta, \dot{\theta}, \mathcal{G}_1, \dot{\mathcal{G}}_1, \mathcal{G}_2, \dot{\mathcal{G}}_2, \psi, \dot{\psi}, \Delta_1, \Delta_2, \Delta_3, \Delta_4, \dot{\Delta}_1, \dot{\Delta}_2, \dot{\Delta}_3, \dot{\Delta}_4, \xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3, \xi_4, \varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3, \varphi_4, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4).$$

The stationary motion of the system is represented in this space by a state of equilibrium.

Conclusion

The system of equations (20) and (27) represent the mathematical model of the curvilinear motion of the car, taking into account the elasticity and deformability of tires (transverse, angular, longitudinal deformation of tires and wheel inclination), as well as non-potential forces in the tire material. The obtained mathematical model makes it possible to fully study the dynamics and stability of systems, taking into account design parameters.

References

1. Turaev Kh.T., Fufaev N.A., Musarsky R.A., Theory of motion of systems with rolling, FAN, Tashkent, 1987, 158 p.
2. Neimark Yu.I., Fufaev N.A., Dynamics of non-holonomic systems, Nauka, Moscow, 1967, 519 p.
3. Turaev Kh.T., Mamatkabilov A.Kh. Computer simulation of the motion of rolling systems. // Collection of abstracts of the III-Congress of mathematicians of the Turkic world. June 30-July 4, 2009, Almaty, Pp.219-220.

4. Turaev Kh.T., Mamatkabilov A.Kh. Dynamic equations of the curvilinear motion of a car. // Scientific Bulletin of SamSU. №5(45), 2007, Pp. 6-13.

5. Mamatkabilov A.Kh., Turaev Kh., Urunbayev E. Automation of output of mathematical model of movement of a car and deformation of its tires. // International training-seminar on mathematics in conjunction with the joint mathematics meeting, 2011 between Samarkand state university and Malaysian mathematical sciences society 3-5 June 2011, Samarkand state university. Pp. 203-207.

6. Mamatkabilov A.Kh. Mathematical model of curvilinear motion on Cylinder wheels. International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science p-ISSN: 2308-4944 (print), e-ISSN: 2409-0085 (online) SOI: 1.1/TAS DOI: 10.15863/TAS. Year: 2020, Issue: 06, Volume: 86, 287-292 pp. Published:22.06.2020, <http://T-Science.org>

7. Mamatkabilov A.Kh. Mathematical models of curved and linear motion of a car taking into account the elasticity and deformable tires. Electronic journal of actual problems of modern science, education and training. August 2021-8/1. Pp. 64-75.

SECOND ORDER SUBDIFFERENTIAL OF FUNCTIONS

Sadygov M.A.

*Doctor of Physical and Mathematical Sciences
Baku State University*

СУБДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛ ВТОРОГО ПОРЯДКА ФУНКЦИЙ

Садыгов М.А.

*доктор физико-математических наук
Бакинский Государственный Университет*

Abstract

The paper considers various definitions of the second-order subdifferential. Their some properties have been studied. The geometric aspects of the 2-subdifferential are considered.

Аннотация

В работе рассматриваются различные определения субдифференциала второго порядка. Изучен ряд их свойств. Рассмотрены геометрические аспекты 2-субдифференциала.

Keywords: bisublinear function, tensor product, operator.

Ключевые слова: бисублинейная функция, тензорное произведение, оператор.

1. Введение

Отметим, что субдифференциал высшего порядка определен в работах автора [1]-[3] и изучен ряд их свойств. Рассмотрены также геометрические аспекты субдифференциала высшего порядка в [3], [4] и [8]. В [1], [2] и [4]-[8] введены класс n -выпуклых функций, n -сублинейных функций, класс n -липшицевых функций, n -выпуклых и n -нормальных множеств, которые подробно изучены автором. Другие определения субдифференциала высшего порядка имеются в работах автора [4] и [8].

В работе рассматриваются определения 2-субдифференциала, бисубдифференциала, обобщенного 2-субдифференциала функции и изучаются их

свойства. Рассмотрены геометрические аспекты 2-субдифференциала и обобщенного 2-субдифференциала функции.

В изучении свойства субдифференциала высшего порядка существенную роль играет аппарат тензорного произведения. В работе используя тензорное произведение изучен ряд свойств субдифференциала второго порядка.

В работе рассматривается определение тензорного произведения, называемого симметричным тензорным произведением пространств. С помощью понятия (симметричного) тензорного произведения пространств изучается ряд свойств (симметричных) четных бисублинейных функций.